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Research Article

**NEUROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY OF HABB-E-SARA A
UNANI FORMULATION AGAINST PTZ INDUCED
CONVULSION IN MICE.**¹Sk. Syed Hussain, ²Bushra Shireen, ³Dr. Anupama Koneru¹Department Of Pharmacology, Sultan-UI-Uloom College Of Pharmacy, Road No.3
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Banjara Hills, Hyderabad 500034, Telangana, India.**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objectives: The present study was carried out to evaluate the neuroprotective activity of HABB-E-SARA a unani formulation against PTZ induced convulsion in mice.

Materials and methods: The epilepsy model used in the study was PTZ induced seizures. The mice of albino strain were divided into five groups with six animals each. Group 1 served as normal; group 2 served as negative control and given PTZ 80mg/kg on the day of screening; group 3 served as standard and given diazepam 4mg/kg; group 4 and 5 were served as test 1 and 2 with doses 2.46mg/kg for test1 and 4.92mg/kg for test2 calculated from human dose of formulation and given in suspension form in 5%CMC. The parameters onset of seizures, duration of convulsion and mortality were assessed. The biochemical parameters like GABA level and antioxidants like SOD, catalase, lipid peroxidation and reduced glutathione in mice brain were analysed and compared statically for different groups.

Results: It was interpreted that treatment with HABB-E-SARA significantly ($p < 0.001$) delayed the onset of seizure and shortens the duration of convulsion and there was 100% protection of animal in both test1 and test2 group.

Key words: HABB E SARA, PTZ, Seizure, GABA, Diazepam, 5%CMC.

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INTRODUCTION:

Epilepsy is a state in which an individual has synchronous abnormal nerve impulses called seizure. A seizure can be termed as irregular, disorganized discharge of nerve impulses resulting in temporary disruption in motor function. Epilepsy originates from the focal region in the brain and its exposition depends on the focal point and the other regions in the brain into which these irregular electrical nerve impulses spread. Seizures are classified, depending primarily on what region of the brain is involved. The term epilepsy does not explain about the type of seizure or cause of these abnormal discharges. Primary or idiopathic epilepsy is termed used for seizure with no underlying cause [1]. Epilepsy is non communicable. Epilepsy has no recognizable cause in about 50% of the population. In the other half, the disease can be due to several factors like genetic influence, head trauma, brain trauma or strokes, infectious diseases and prenatal injury [2].

It is reckoned that there are more than 10,000 persons with epilepsy in India. The number of cases is higher in rural (1.9%) compared to cities (0.6%). In the Bangalore Urban Rural Neuro-epidemiological survey (BURNS), a prevalence rate of 8.8/1000 people was scrutinized, with the rate in less developed areas (11.9) and (5.7) in city. Poverty is a major risk and involves both being from a poor country and being indigent relative to others within ones country. In the developed nations epilepsy is mostly seen in either young or in old. In the emerging nation its onset is more prevalent in adolescents and in young adults due increased rates of infectious diseases and trauma. In developed nations, prevalence has declined in the children and increased among the older age between 1970s and 2003. This has been accredited moderately to better survival following strokes in the geriatric population [3].

Epilepsy treatment with daily medication is usually initiated when a second seizure has occurred [4]. The treatment include, drugs which act on ion channels like phenytoin, carbamazepine, ethosuximide, valproic acid, drugs which inhibit EAA transmission like felbamate and topiramate and the drugs which enhance GABA transmission like benzodiazepines, gabapentin, vigabatrin and barbiturates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Animals:**

Swiss albino mice strain (25-30gm) was procured from Sainath Animal Agency, Musheerabad, Hyderabad, India. The mice were kept under standard well controlled conditions i.e., temperature 22° (±3), humidity 50-60% throughout

the experimental duration. The animals were given Pellet diet with drinking water ad libitum, kept under 12h/h light dark cycle and maintained for at least 5 days prior to dosing allow for acclimatization to laboratory conditions. The experimental protocol was given approval by Institutional animal ethics committee and was carried under the compliance of IAEC guidelines. (IAEC/SUCP/2019/04)

Drugs:

The formulation HABB-E-SARA was obtained as research sample from Asian unani pharmacy, Shah Ali Banda, Hyderabad, Telangana, India and was used as received. Habb-e-Sara contains Aloe barbedensis 33.3mg (sibr-e-aloe), Boswellia serrata 33.3mg (kundur), and Castoreum 33.3mg (jund baid-e- star)

Diazepam (Ranbaxy, India)

Pentylentetrazole (sigma Aldrich, India)

Carboxy methyl cellulose (s-d fine chemical Ltd)

METHODOLOGY:**PTZ- induced seizure model:**

For this method, the Mice were divided into 5 groups of 6 animals each. They had free access to regular mice chow and water ad libitum for 21 days.

GROUP 1: 5% CMC (p.o)

GROUP 2: PTZ (80mg/kg) in normal saline (i.p)

GROUP 3: Diazepam (5mg/kg) in normal saline (i.p)

GROUP 4: Test dose 1(2.96mg/kg) in 5% CMC (p.o)

GROUP 5: Test dose 2 (4.92 mg/kg) in 5% CMC (p.o)

The test doses 1st and 2nd were administered orally daily for 21 days based on their body weight. On the 22nd day the animals as usual received test doses and after 60 mins of administration of test and standard, PTZ (80mg/kg) was given to all groups except group 1. Immediately after the PTZ administration Mice were observed for next 30 min for following symptoms, Onset of convulsions, duration of convulsions and mortality [5].

ESTIMATION OF BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

Brain tissue homogenate preparation: Mice were sacrificed by decapitation and the skull was exposed and brains were removed carefully and transferred to Petri plates containing ice-cold isotonic buffer saline. Then the brain samples were

then homogenized with ice cold 0.1M phosphate buffer (ph 7.4) in a volume 10 folds the weight of tissue. The homogenate was centrifuged at 3000rpm for 15 min and aliquots of supernatant were used for estimation of following biochemical parameters [6].

Estimation of GABA:

GABA concentration was measured by the method of Lowe et.al [7]

Procedure:

The separated brain was placed in 5ml of 10% ice cold trichloroacetic acid, then homogenised and centrifuged at 10,000rpm for 10min at 0°C. the homogenised sample was then placed in 0.2ml of 0.14 M ninhydrin solution in 0.5M carbonate-bicarbonate buffer(ph9.95), and kept in water bath at 60c for half an hour, then cooled at room temperature and treated with 5ml copper tartarate reagent and the absorbance were measured after 10 min at 377/455nm

Estimation of super oxide dismutase

This method was introduced by Mishra and Frideovich [8]

Procedure:

0.1ml of supernatant from the centrifuged tissue brain homogenate was taken and to it 0.5ml of carbonate buffer of pH9.7 was prepared freshly and added. To the above mixture 1ml of epinephrine (1mM) was added. The optical density was read at 480nm for 3mins. The enzyme activity was expressed in terms of U/min/mg.

Estimation of Catalase activity:

Catalase estimation was by method of Aebi [9]

Procedure:

To 0.1ml of tissue homogenate add 2.25ml of potassium phosphate buffer and incubate at 25c for 30min. The reaction was initiated by adding 0.65ml H₂O₂. The blank was prepared by using 2.5ml potassium phosphate buffer and 0.65ml hydrogen

peroxide. Absorbance was measure at 240nm for 2-3 mins.

Estimation of Lipid peroxidation

Lipid peroxide concentration of homogenate was estimated by measuring the amounts of maliondaaldehyde (MDA) by using thio barbutric acid reaction as demonstrated by okhawa et al [10-13]

Procedure:

1ml tissue homogenate, 0.2 ml SLS solution, 1.5 ml 20% acetic acid and 1.5 ml TBA solution is taken and made up to 5ml. incubate for few minutes and then heated in boiling water bath for 30 min. n-butanol and pyridine mixture was added to extract the chromagen, then centrifuge at 4000rpm for 10 min. Absorbance of organic layer was measured at 532nm

Estimation of Reduced Glutathione:

Reduced glutathione (GSH) level was measured using the method described by Ellman [14-16]

Procedure:

To the tissue homogenate, equal volume of 20% trichloroacetic acid containing 1Mm EDTA was added. Mixture was allowed to incubate for 5min at room temperature, and then centrifugation was done at 200rpm for 10 minutes.0.2ml of supernatant was taken in fresh test tubes. Ellman's reagent (0.1Mm) containing 1% sodium citrate was added to above mixture and make up the volume to 2ml. Absorbance was read at 412nm against blank.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained by the different parameters was statistically evaluated by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) by Graph pad prism software (Graph pad software inc., version 8.2.0). The parameters were expressed in mean value \pm SEM and the level of significance was found to be $p < 0.001$.

Onset of seizure:

Figure 1: Graph Showing Increased Latency In The Onset Of Seizure In Test 1 And Test 2

Duration of seizure:

Figure 2: Graph Showing The Decrease In Frequency In The Duration Of Seizures In Test 1 And Test 2

Estimation of GABA:

Figure 3: Graph Showing Increase In GABA Level In Test 1 And Test 2

Estimation of SOD:

Figure 4: Graph Showing Increase In SOD Level In Test 1 And Test 2

Estimation of catalase:

Figure 5: Graph Showing Increase Catalase Level In Test 1 And Test 2

Estimation of lipid Peroxidation:

Figure 6: Graph Showing Decrease In Lipid Peroxidation In Test1 And Test 2

Estimation of Reduced Glutathione:

Figure 7: Graph Showing Increase Glutathione Level In Test 1 And Test 2

DISCUSSION:

Regulation of seizures is the principal curative in the management of convulsions. Around 40% of patient with epilepsy are in compliance to the interceding of antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) and thus their safety and efficacy remains elusive. Besides, none of the dated or novel AEDs emerge to represent an efficacious way for preventing epilepsy or its advancement. That is why; there is imperative need for additional research especially in the field of drug treatment of epilepsy to discover drugs which are not only antiepileptic but also antiepileptogenic

Herbal formulation has the potential to be an infinite source for safer and more effective, economical and culturally acceptable antiepileptic compounds, especially in poor regions. The present work investigates the neuroprotective effect of Habb-e-Sara a Unani formulation, consisting of extract from the plants, i.e., *Aloe barbadensis* (sibre-aloee), *Boswellia Serrata* (kundur), and *castoreum* (Jund baid-astar). The low and high dose of formulation was calculated from the maximum daily dose given in human. The test dose 1 and 2 shows significant result by delaying the onset of seizures, shortening the duration and showed 100% protection against seizure.

The GABA-benzodiazepine site is the main target in the treatment of epilepsy, as it increases the sensitivity of the GABA receptor for indigenous GABA. When GABA binds to a target, the Cl^- channel ion influx is increased and an anticonvulsant activity is achieved. In our study the unani formulation had shown dose dependent significant

($p < 0.001$) increment in the GABA levels in mice brain.

Free radicals have been alluded to be the agent held for producing the neurologic changes intervening the behavioural shortfall in neurodegeneration. Lot of studies proved that antioxidants are effective in the animal model of epilepsy. Oxygen is vital for many aerobic cellular process but it may go through electron transfer chain which produces highly reactive oxygen free radicals such as hydrogen peroxide and super oxide anion. The nerve cells are extremely sensitive to oxidative injury caused by these reactive species. The low and high dose of habbe-sara significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased the super oxide dismutase and catalase level in brain.

Lipid peroxidation is well defined mechanism of cellular in both plants and animal and is used as marker of oxidative damage in tissues and cells. The lipid peroxidation is estimated by several methods out of which TBA reactive substance is chosen because of its simplicity in working and high sensitivity. In the current study, the formulation showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) low level of MDA in lipid peroxidation.

Glutathione is an indigenous antioxidant found abundantly intracellular thiol and low molecular weight tripeptides present in living cells. It prevents the formation of singlet oxygen or hydroxyl radical by reacting with free radicals. Oxidative neuronal death of brain cell is due to depletion of glutathione. The low level of GSH seen in diseased group of mice in the current study suggest that there was an enhanced generation of free radicals and GSH was decreased in this process combating

oxidative damage. Test dose 1 and 2 significantly ($p < 0.001$) elevated GSH level in mice brain.

Histopathological study revealed that test doses 1 and 2 of Habb-e-Sara shows positive interpretation showing normal brain cortex, meninges of brain and cerebellum appear clear and no hippocampal haemorrhages when compared with the negative control brain which reveals the moderate degeneration of neurons in hippocampus region and mild haemorrhage.

Elevated GABA and antioxidants like SOD, catalase, reduced glutathione and reduction in lipid peroxidation justifies the neuroprotective effect of Habb-e-Sara. All the results were statistically significant with $p > 0.001$ showing excellent therapeutic effect and giving it evidence for its use in absence seizures other than febrile convulsions.

CONCLUSION:

Alternative medicinal practices have remained as a component of the health care system of many societies despite well - established alternatives. Herbal medicines on the whole have a broad spectrum because they have variety of bioactive compounds. It is worth taking into an account that most of the extracts tested were chosen based on knowledge that they are traditionally used against other ailments or as antiepileptic by traditional herbalist. Although herbs have been used for decades and tested in preclinical trials, there is a lack of accreditation and safety efficacy studies, restricting their usage in present-day medicine.

For a drug to be an effective anticonvulsant, it should cross the blood-CSF barrier. Choosing the appropriate animal model is a crucial factor in the case of misleading results as different models could simulate different types of epilepsy. Maximal electroshock (MES) and pentylenetetrazol (PTZ) are the two most commonly used methods in screening natural compounds for antiepileptic activity. Positive results in both the model suggest that the test compound or its metabolite crossed the blood-brain barrier and exerted its effect on the central nervous system. Testing a substance in distinct model accord more holistic idea of the substance's efficacy as each model imitates a different form of epilepsy and thus a distinct mechanism of action of test extract.

In conclusion, we have found that administration of the Unani formulation Habb-e-Sara for 21 days had elevated the seizure threshold in mice and its possible mode of action is mediated through GABA receptors.

The safety and efficacy of AED's is still a matter of concern. For testing new drugs, animal models have been used since time immemorial, and are continually becoming more sophisticated as

technology and scientific understanding ahead. We evaluated the formulation in animal model, and it showed positive results, it's used is confined to febrile seizure but from our study it shows effective result in absence seizures; furthermore, studies are need to be exhorted to help the legacy of herbal drugs to achieve more impact and endorsement.

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